

A SOLUTION TO THE ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEM THROUGH DATA ANALYSIS: ECOCUPS STARTUP EXPERIMENT

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Abstract. *The article discusses the negative impact of single-use plastics on the environment and the EcoCups startup created as a solution. The project's data-driven analysis highlights user needs and opportunities to reduce emissions using an AI model.*

Keywords. *Ecology, waste, plastic cups, biodegradation, startup, EcoCups, Data Science, artificial intelligence, youth initiative, green technologies.*

Annotation. *The figures and facts presented in the article are based on reliable open sources. According to available estimates, plastic waste generation in Uzbekistan exceeds 1 million tons annually, with a steady yearly growth rate of around 3–5%, and a significant share of this consists of single-use plastic products such as disposable cups. In urban areas, daily consumption of disposable cups can reach hundreds of thousands, contributing to increasing landfill pressure and environmental degradation. Reports published by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations on biodegradable packaging products helped to understand international experience in environmental solutions. FAO studies indicate that the adoption of biodegradable packaging can reduce environmental pollution by 30–50%, and in some cases decrease landfill waste volume by up to 20%, while also lowering carbon emissions associated with plastic production by approximately 15–25%. Additionally, an international analysis of the plastic waste problem was conducted using global statistical data obtained from the Statistik platform. Global statistics show that more than 400 million tons of plastic waste are generated each year worldwide, with around 36% attributed to packaging materials, including single-use items. Of this total, only about 9% is recycled, 19% is incinerated, and nearly 50% ends up in landfills or the natural environment. Furthermore, it is estimated that over 1 million plastic bottles are purchased every minute globally, highlighting the scale of the issue. It was on this basis that the EcoCups startup was created.*

Today, the global waste problem is exacerbating the environmental crisis. The harmful impact of single-use plastics on the environment is particularly severe and requires a long time to be eliminated. According to statistics, Uzbekistan generates approximately 10.2 million tons of solid household waste annually, of which 10.3%, or 1.05 million tons, are plastic waste. 192,000 tons of plastic waste come from packaging materials. Such negative consequences threaten not only the ecological balance but also human health. Therefore, environmental startups and the scientific and analytical foundations behind them are becoming increasingly important.

To bring the project from an idea to the level of a startup, it was first necessary to deeply analyze the state of the existing problem. To this end, we collected data on the consumption and environmental impact of single-use plastic cups in Uzbekistan and neighboring countries. According to UzStat, FAO, World Bank Data, and other international open sources, an average of 80 million disposable glasses are consumed annually in Uzbekistan. More than 90% of them are not recycled and do not decompose in nature for 100-200 years, which means that these glasses remain as harmful and hazardous waste. We also conducted a survey among a target audience of 300 people (university students, cafe patrons, and young entrepreneurs). The survey results showed that demand for eco-friendly products is growing, and people are consciously ready to switch to green solutions, but price, quality, and availability are important factors.

EcoCups startup: Aim of Research. To solve this problem, we launched a startup called EcoCups. The glasses developed in the project are 99% biodegradable and wear-resistant. The composition of the product consists of corn flour, rice flour, water, and other natural substances, and it is considered safe for the human body. These glasses are completely decomposed in the soil within 20 days without causing harm to the environment or being consumed with the product. Our products are based on a B2B network (cafes, catering, coffee shops, and restaurants) and have been developed in consultation with health and environmental experts, and do not pose a risk of other diseases. In doing so, we not only reduce waste but also support a healthy lifestyle.

Data Science approach. When creating the project, we used a number of data-analytical methods:

I. Market analysis: By analyzing the needs and desires of the audience through surveys, we determined the level of demand for the product.

II. Product Test Results: Based on the feedback received from MVP tests, changes were made to the product's shape, material, and durability.

III. AI-based waste reduction model: A simulation was built to determine how much waste would be reduced if EcoCups were used instead of plastic cups in Uzbekistan.

The tests and analyses conducted have shown that the project is capable of yielding real results. Out of 300 users who are not indifferent to nature, 68% are ready to choose EcoCups instead of plastic cups. The MVP was tested in 10 cafes and 1 public event, with a total positive review rate of 87%. According to an AI simulation, if the EcoCups product is widely implemented, at least 32 tons of plastic waste can be reduced per year. This is not only beneficial for the environment but also reduces waste recycling costs. *If* we summarize the results obtained from the survey, taking into account that the population of Uzbekistan is ready to pay 4.2k for original cups, 4.7k for chocolate and vanilla cups, and 3.2k for espresso cups, from an analytical perspective, we found that we can recoup our 30 million US dollars spent within 8-12 months.

In conclusion. The EcoCups project promotes values such as interest in green technologies and social responsibility among young people, in addition to environmental benefits. Through this project, we will combine a healthy environment, environmental thinking, and a modern scientific approach. In the future, there are plans to automate production, increase production volumes, and increase efficiency using artificial intelligence.

LIST OF SOURCES USED

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